

THE REVIVAL OF LONG READING: A NEW MULTIMODAL NARRATIVE FORMAT

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The goal of this study is to specify nature, the “heart and soul” of a process referred to as a “long reading”, to indentify reasons for the interest in the so-called longread narrative formats, unexpectedly going up in times of obviously reverse trends, such as, for example, short and speed reading techniques. The key research findings indicate that longread formats are increasingly more and more popular, as these texts enable readers to keep out of the information pollution. The outcomes and conclusions are focusing on expanding the conceptional fields towards new policies stimulating reading and to more creative methods producing reading effects into the sphere of quality online journalism, education, publishing industries and popularization of science, at large.

Keywords: studies of reading, communication studies, multimodal reading, multimodal writing, longread format, long text, longform essay, longform journalism

INTRODUCTION

The actual field of reading and book sciences reveals inevitable implications of digitization of reading and also generalizes empirical evidence of the changing of reading practices. Having this in mind, we have initialized the present research; its objects are the return to the longread formats or the reflexive move towards saga, epics, series, but in the online environment. As a subject of immediate interest is the target group dealing with longread media formats, described as non-reading people whose brains are functioning in a different way: they cannot apprehend big-size texts, their attention is strongly disorganized (fluctuation, instability, dispersion and scattering) and symptomatic impatient expectancy, their imagination is badly developed, their thinking is rather formal, they are losing ability for complex logic functions and in-depth analyses. Research motivation pathfinder has been the necessity to find lines for

the world publishers on which they to focus in order ‘to attract reader’s attention’. The Smart publishers have the chance to stimulate even elder non-readers to read.

Actuality and significance of the topic. At first glance, one apprehends the popular and incontestable thesis claiming that online environment encourages the simple manner of information collection and does not stimulate the fact memorization, that it favors a type of fragmented thinking from the standpoint of the segmented information only and does not develop a systematic manner of thinking on long synthesized knowledge excerpts. There is an imposed irrational consensus about generalization claiming that in the era of digital letters long reading is an exercise for monks – it might be an activity of a person, isolated in the oasis of religious seclusion and loneliness, a practice for hermits. It seems, long reading has been left for the men of God in the monasteries – reading scriptures, liturgical books and reading activities, specific for the monastery cells and habits. At the same time, we are getting more and more feeble-minded surfing in the Net. Maryanne Wolf, professor of child studies and human development psychology, director of the Center for Reading and Language Research at Tufts University, and author of the monograph „Proust and the Squid: The Story and Science of the Reading Brain” (Wolf 2015), has become popular with her concept that the style of reading, acquired in Internet, subservient to efficacy and speed, may invalidate our capability to read implicitly and in-depth, adopted by the human beings in the time of the previous revolutionary media technology – print press, when long and complex prose has been commonly used, free-for-all. M. Wolf is anxious about „the time-consuming demands of the deep-reading processes will be lost in a culture whose principal mediums advantage speed, multitasking, and processing the next piece of information,” ... „confronted with a digital glut of immediate information that requires and receives less and less intellectual effort, many readers will have neither the time nor the motivation to think through the possible layers of meaning in what they read.” (Baron 2015: 167). The human capacity to interpret texts, to creates rich mental associations and forms connections, while reading concentratedly and for long, cannot be activated, to a great extent.

Scholarly necessity and innovation of the issue. The study is innovative in the current global context: each year the results, obtained, about the reading abilities (measured through the PISA, PIRLS, TIMSS methodologies) are negative; and if so, it is a means to correct the unsuccessful methodologies, offered, from the perspective of e-reading ecology and hygiene

(Tsvetkova 2016c). This research is wanted if we wish to re-think the large-scale dispersed, non-coherent knowledge concerning reading.

METHODOLOGY

The research method of the study, submitted, is a comprehensive systematization of particular qualitative and quantitative methods, such as review of recent theoretical investigations, systematic review, critical analysis, and also bibliographic monitoring and bibliometric analysis. The primary research data are supplied through chronological empirical studies of industry of reading, generally, and also via monitoring of innovation in techniques, technologies and marketing practices in the book business, media monitoring of renown online periodicals, bibliographic systematization of bestsellers and also publicly communicated governmental documents, researches in cognitive science and sociological studies on various specific issues made by the marketing agencies. As a source for the secondary data – the theoretical grounds of the critical analysis, we have used works and concepts of scholars in the fields of evolution theory of reading and written communication, such as Maryanne Wolf, Naomi Baron, Paul Lester, Gunther Kress, Jennifer Rowsell, Sigrid Fahrer, El Lissitzky, Robert Darnton, Umberto Eco, Alan Jacobs, Julia Melentieva, Anne Mangen, Dobrinka Peicheva, etc.

As analytic objects are explored factors and rational motives for the change in communication formats of online reading that have happened since 2009, noted as longread media formats. The research goal is to reveal a new perspective toward the active reader's problems and the e-reading which we consider as urgent for rethinking, actualization and revision. The concrete aims of this report are to search for arguments and evidence from communicative viewpoint and in the outcomes of the sociological studies, and to summarize the factors that could be considered as an inception for this unexpected redesign of the online reading object. Having in mind the difficulty to be an unbiased and unprejudiced researcher while dealing with reading issues, I have tried to minimize my personal viewpoint, anyway. The leading standpoint of the study is ensued from the belief that if we would want to live together and to work with rationally and proactively thinking persons, if we would like to set up a governing elite in the knowledge economy, we are obliged to eliminate the factors that may

have detaining effects, such as prohibition and exclusion, and to stimulate the intensification agents in the field of reader's intelligence.

CONCEPT AND TERMS

The term 'reading' in the current text is used in its informative and communicative sense (Tsvetkova 2001; 2009). In accordance with the now actual paradigm for the new literacies, reading is a process of mediated informativity using letters as symbols, but not necessarily, and carried out via the eyes, but not necessarily (for ex. audio reading or tactile reading in the case of blind people). This is an extension of the term 'reading' and it has appeared as a result of the expansion of the other term, namely literacy, in the last 10 years; during this time the process has focused on the vision that the term 'reader' should cover and include everybody who participates in online and mobile communications.

An important step to this conceptual liberalization has been the proposal of the German Fund Stiftung Lesen Fund made during the „Digitale Medien: Chancen für das Lesen“ Symposium, 2014, for extending interpretation of the term 'reading'. Up to that moment it was used just to indicate 'reading of fiction in the leisure time', as Dr. Sigrid Fahrer explained. And as an actual fact, everyone surfing in internet space is also a reader; one who follows the iconic navigations in the websites is also a reader; the person who reads the rules and instructions, video game participant – all are readers as well and if they are not able to read they are dropping out of the game. Taking into consideration the alarming fact that Germany has 7,5 mln. illiterates, then it is necessary the term reading to include digital media, internet publications, Facebook and all possible computer devices and applications. D-r Fahrer argues also that if a videogame booster or protagonist realizes that s/he is a reader, this may give him/her more confidence and may increase his/her satisfaction from reading as a process. (Fahrer 2014)

The year of 2015 registered a new development in the expert reflexion on 'reading – visual perception' relation. It happened during the European Conference on „Literacy in the New Landscape of Communication: Research, Education and the Everyday“, organized by the Austrian Literacy Association, Klagenfurt, Austria. At this meeting, for example, Dr. Jennifer Rowsell from Brock University, Canada, has stood up for the proposition that we should redefine terms such as writer and reader since today reading is even more connected to listening

and watching as processes. In her view, the way in which young people use mobile applications is a new form of reading and writing competences. Her vision is based on findings from a comparative study of school curricula in 21 countries and on the innovative reading conception carried out by the US and UK education systems. Indeed, the findings from the questionnaire circulated during the respective Forum have demonstrated that most of its participants are ready to accept the movies, podcasts, applications and videogames as reading formats. (Rowse 2015)

Today we define photo-visual literacy as an art of reading visual representations; this definition is a 'fruit' of the new perception of traditional term 'reading' extended to a 'reading' without letters, and it is considered a theoretical contribution (Eshet-Alkalai 2004: 93-106). It is well known fact that even in the end of the 20th century the communications have been 'iconized' – the images were liberated from the confinement of the verbal texts and demonstrated they might transmit the media contents even independently. Moreover, today in many cases the verbal text illustrates the images (Kaftandzhiev 1996: 7, 98). The 'optic journalism' concept has been introduced into the media field in the beginning of the 21st century and in accordance with it the image is interpreted as an 'entrance' to the very text; then a consensus has been reached among the professional guild that, necessarily, writing, design and editing of the sites should be put on the track not only to the reading or checking quickly the pages audiences but also to the watching audiences. Text, photo and picture, graphics do have different powers and functions; and in this case all comprehensive processes and complex dependencies may be presented in front of the reader enough sufficiently and understandably only by photos, pictures and infographics, expounds V. Vulkanova (2001). The leaders in the experimenting print media group highly valued the photos not only for their attractiveness, authentic fast carrying information capacity but also for their efficacy while creating the so-called 'visual interest centers'. „Infographics suggests readers direct access and much more great freedom, while using the data offered, through extracting the likeness and contrast issues they are interested in“ (Vulkanova 2001: 42). The online environment of the readers sitting in front of the display every day has to prove how the images, included in a publication, may attract attention and become reason it to be read.

We may see how in the context of internet and visual communications 'a new composed figure is actively moulded and this is the figure of the 'reader-viewer-listener' of books (texts);

its activity should not be evaluated in compliance with the standards of past, writes J. Melentieva, Russian professor in theory of reading (Melentieva 2010: 71). In agreement with Norman Doidge's theory of the plastic brain (Doidge 2015) and in conformity to the laws and principles of evolution of reading, we should recognize that human receptive apparatus today is intensively self-educating and muting; books and texts are apprehended in a very new, different way.

So, in the process of redefining reading we shape an evolution, which is enough as an argument to claim that this term should be reconsidered as a new media reception type, which includes optic reading and parareading beyond contact with any written text. In accordance to actual development of the theoretical conventions, by 'reading' we should understand a reception process where three basic clauses of the triad 'content-code-reception' are fulfilled: it is possible to read each artificially created content, indicated by whatever symbol system, and which has passed through analytic and synthetic processing in the brain structures in charge of reading. In the term 'reader' we shall put in every subject capable to absorb and acquire a text addressed to him/her and who performs this act without interruption, actively and over and over again. (Tsvetkova 2016c)

RESULTS

Harry Potter: the herald of longread

In 1997 when the troubles of the 'media cannibal' No 1 of reading, the television, were projected on the 'media cannibal' No 2 of reading, the computer, unexpectedly children were fascinated by the books. Moreover, those books were formatted as for adults: 1) large in size, 2) thick, 3) small in face; and 4) without any illustration. Long before the term 'longread' to be legitimized, a longread book mapped out the future of the next qualitative media formats. Bibliometric analysis of the published Harry Potter series bestsellers (*Table 1*) demonstrates, so it seemed then, endless interest of the 'new young' to the long reading matters.

Table 1. Bibliometric book systematization of Harry Potter series

Print book	Language	Book Title	Publication Year	Page Count
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Book 1	English	Harry Potter and the Philosopher's Stone	1997	223 p.
	Bulgarian	Хари Потър и философският камък	2000	264 s.
Book 2	English	Harry Potter and the Chamber of Secrets	1998	366 p.
	Bulgarian	Хари Потър и стаята на тайните	2001	295 s.
Book 3	English	Harry Potter and Prisoner of Azkaban	1999	468 p.
	Bulgarian	Хари Потър и затворникът от Азкабан	2001	367 s.
Book 4	English	Harry Potter and the Goblet of Fire	2000	636 p.
	Bulgarian	Хари Потър и Огненият бокал	2002	600 s.
Book 5	English	Harry Potter and the Order of the Phoenix	2003	766 p.
	Bulgarian	Хари Потър и Орденът на феникса	2004	856 s.
Book 6	English	Harry Potter and the Half-Blood Prince	2005	607 p.
	Bulgarian	Хари Потър и Нечистокръвния принц	2005	576 s.
Book 7	English	Harry Potter and the Deathly Hallows	2007	607 p.
	Bulgarian	Хари Потър и даровете на Смъртта	2007	656 s.

Longread Net: the milestone of ‘lengthy twist’ in the reading proposals

Longread is an innovation that collaborates various journalistic formats, styles and topics. The media content publishers use this new method while searching for different viewpoints as arguments. Virtually, its core activity is to collect stories from different authors and independent publishers. The written text is presented in an aggregate, ‘orchestrated’ in an entity together with words, static and dynamic images, motion graphics, sound effects, audio documentary, photos, videos, animated and interactive infographics, video infographics, i.e. via multimedia presentation of the traditional information in a new, relatively longer version. In this case more than one human sense is included in the perception and so, it becomes the ground on which the personal attention is kept; this behavioral and cognitive process usually is changeable and unstable while dealing with tedious and dull texts.

In fact, Longread began as a blogged idea in the Word Press Site. The startup of this innovation was in the year of 2009 and the creator’s name was Mike Armstrong. He has shared the longread concept as follows: „All that is Longread is a mixture of writers and topics; and this, exactly, is a part of our DNA. Well-known authors and less-known authors are distinguishing themselves from the big corporations of the big money. This is the reason why such authors offer their readers better quality.” (Longreads 2014) Step-by-step, the blog has brought together different authors and formed an online community, bound up in the rising of qualitative writing and reading. Since 2017 Longread has its own site, namely Longreads.com, and an own slogan - „The best place for long stories in the Net”. In order the network to be able to function, the independent writers have been invited to subscribe just for \$30. The team is of four enthusiasts and their main goal is to create a sustainable membership, enough sufficient resources to invest in collecting and publicly communicating stories, competitive with the best world newspapers and magazines. More members, more authors will share their stories and, consequently, greater variety and chance to select. The articles follow the basic characteristics of the longread narrative – the text is of above 1500 characters, color illustrations in cartoon-style or documentary photos and multimedia applications.

The first world qualitative journalism longread was a publication in *The New York Times Online*, 2012, entitled ‘Snow Fall. The Avalanche at Tunnel Creek’ (Branch 2012). In Russian,

since 2014 there have been sections with multimedia longreads in the publications of the TASS, InoSMI, Argumenty i Fakty, „Kommersant”, „Komsomolskaya Pravda”, „Populyarnaya Mehanika”. Today there are many platforms for content-oriented web projects in longread formats (articles, special projects, sites, landing pages), such as tilda.cc, shorthand.com, creatavist.com, readymag.com, stampsy.com, medium.com. All of them are privileged to serve the readers who want to read something substantial, true, reliable and long, something longer than the usual journalistic article and shorter than a book.

For the purposes of this study we use the chronological method to systemize the long-drawn-out process presupposing the revival of the long reading. We shall call it the ‘lengthy twist’ of the proposals for reading.

TIMELINE

of ‘Lengthy Twist’ in the Reading Proposals

1968: „Easy-to-read” – innovative publishing technology for redesign of newspapers, books and textbooks in an ‘easy-to-read’ format; first come into view in Sweden, then in the Netherlands, Finland, the United Kingdom and France. This format bets to the short and light, quick and easy reading while changing the policy of formatting headlines and titles, illustrations, column cutting down, lettering size (font size, typeface size) increase, etc.

1970–1982: Infographics is licensed and introduced into the popular mass media. Up to that moment huge amounts of knowledge, almost the whole human knowledge, *de facto*, has been deposited for safekeeping in a ‘longread’ format. The registered exponential growth of publications produces enormous content and society has no time to read the usual ‘long content’ (the so-called ‘thick and long books’). The technological revolution holds out a new perception. Infographics and its capacity to spare readers’ time is fitting well for the new era trend - fast and fun. In the terms of „fast’n’fun” it is already possible to write and to read without letters. *The USA Today* is among the first newspapers that have implied infographics (a graphic-text composition). This has happened in 1982 and just few years later this daily has entered the Big5 most popular US newspapers. American readers very soon have assessed the quality of this publishing technique: infographics transmits messages faster than the text in letters (a qualified image may replace several textual pages) and is even more detailed than the standard photography (due to the particularity of the picture and the exact thesis notes).

1980: „Drabble” – a special narrative format of 100 words, implemented by Birmingham University (UK) as a type of verbal game used to check author’s ability to express a whole complete concept in an extremely short form. After 1987 the cannon has been

reconsidered by cutting down the size to 55 words and continuing the format's life under the form of a literature competition.

1997–2007: „Harry Potter” Book Series – the milestone of the ‘lengthy twist’ in the proposals for paper book reading parallelly with the „Third Golden Age of Television”.

2000: „Key to the Classics” – a series of compressed extracted books, produced by the American Publishing House „Cliffs Notes”; more than 300 concise classical works were published in a size from 40 up to 200 pages; in Bulgaria the model was reproduced by „Trud Publishing House” (14 book published between 2006 and 2010).

2005: „The 100-Minute Bible“ - concise publication of the Holly Book; it should be ‘read at a gallop’, its author is Martin Hinton, British clergyman.

2006: Tweets and Twitterature – publications in the social network in maximum 140 symbols.

2009: 60second Recap – compressed video books; more exactly, short video summaries of books, their length is 60 seconds (for ex., Dostoevsky's *Crime and Punishment* in 60second Recap).

2009: Mike Armstrong's Longreads blog – the milestone of the ‘lengthy twist’ in the proposals for online reading.

2010-2011: Instant publishing, a new line for „effectively published books” in e-version – concise books, collection criterion is the issue to be narrow and ‘hot’, cheap prices; a short format, intermediate between the long magazine article and a book, with extra items added in relation to the main topic and active utilization of the available editorial archives and documentaries – all these add a value to the text just because of the so-called retrospective journey in the topic history.

2011: „Seven Classic Books Read in 35 Seconds” – pictographic books on one page; a production of the Italian Design Studio H-5bb7 as an element of the album, entitled „Life in Five Seconds: Over 200 Stories For Those With No Time to Waste”.

2011: Amazon's Kindle Singles, a middle-size book program (Mini-Books for iPad and iPhone), each volume is between 5000 and 30 000 words (30-90 pages), advertised as „convincing stories told in their natural size”.

2011: TED Books, together with Kindle Singles – e-books of TED Conference lecturers; each TED Book consists of approximately 20 000 words; its length ‘allows you to see the idea developed in a satisfactory way and without the need to dedicate one week to read it’.

2012: „Snow Fall. The Avalanche at Tunnel Creek“ – *The New York Times* Longread Story; the first full-valued longread in the qualitative online journalism.

2016, September: Twitter has released sharing of pictures, videos, GIFs, votings and citations of other tweets from the existing limitation rule for up to 140 symbols.

2016: Instant Articles in Facebook format in News Feed FYI (FYI = "For Your Information") – a new algorithm of this platform for news longread (News Feed 2016); longread format enriched by video, interactive maps, 3D photos and pictures, convenient for reading without leaving Facebook (Weinberg 2016).

2016: Editions at Play – a digital hub for books formatted as „3-hour time to read”; it is said, this hub consists of „books that cannot be printed”, as they are specially created to be read via internet by using phone or tablet; these are books-websites, created for mobile devices by Records Company in cooperation with Penguin Random House (UK) for the fans of in-depth journalism. The first work title is „Strata”, a cinematographic hybrid between science and fantasy.

2017: Facebook starts a new algorithm for longread format, named "Instant Articles" (Wen 2017).

2017, November: Twitter doubles the released limit of 140 characters to 280 per post.

Nature of Modern Longread

Longread means a reading with a style. Longread means a reading while assembling design choreography and symphony with multimodal orchestration and arrangement. Text proposal is synchronized with the actual trend of 'conservative modernism' – a revival of the value of the charming, sensible and long contemplated objects.

Format peculiarities of Longread product:

- besides author, longread publication needs a producer as well;
- it is an innovative text format that has started experimenting in HTML5 code;
- parallax effect with CSS (used parallax scrolling as a conduit for storytelling);
- uninterrupted text on one and the same page;
- the text is over 1500-2000 words (9000–12 000 characters, 3–4 pages) but it, possibly, may reach up to 10 000 words (60 000 characters, 35–40 pages);
- colored photos, charts, maps;
- specific caricature stylistics;
- Gifs or pictures;
- animated scenes;

- infographics;
- sound effects;
- audio or recorded spoken voice;
- videos.

Rules to hold back reader's attention as long as possible:

- more air, blank space around the texts;
- shorter paragraphs;
- larger fonts;
- text-boxes;
- bullets;
- sound (noise) effects that may increase interest to the plot (typically for children);
- it develops digital reading manners and methods;
- „long“ format is a harmony of delicately balanced expression, functionality and readability;
- One new moment: it combines the narrow text column and the vertical video.

Readers' demands to the publisher:

- A terrible story to be told;
- Interactive components to be distinct from the text;
- No elements to distract reader's attention;
- A 'pure' design. (Edenspiekermann 2017)

The content analytic techniques may be applied to any generated and generalized massif of longread publications in virtue of already worked out basic format features that are consistent with the reader's demands (*Table 2*).

Table 2. Content analysis matrix of longread publications (Kolesnichenko 2015)

№	Publication title	Bibliographic data (edition, issue, date, pages)	Topic	Words and characters amount	Number cited resources	Number examples, stories	Report fragments	Number transitions from general to private and vice versa in a zig-zag composition	Infographics demonstrating the expert capacity in the respective thematic field	Multimedia displaying transmedia competence of the respective producer team
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Long writing stories formats, such as multimedia „longread”, will be successful in the knowledge era not just because they can transfer the same content from one media carrier to another but also because they may change their features. Longread format saves the textual part but provides a virtual reality as a supplement to the text (dynamic illustrations, maps, videos), and meanwhile it plays the role of a content filter. People’s attention and time are limited resources and because of this longread creators emphasize on both, supplementing virtuality and going in-depth into the very essence of the work via its long form.

Longread is a niche, non-mastered yet by the publishers and advertisers. As the attention duration of the average navigating user is limited, the reception of high metrics, i.e. publication eyesight, is not necessary to be carried as a good indication of reader’s interest. However, the readers are going back to their longread authors, again and again. And obviously, longread format contains much more space for any intentional advertisement. Since the very substance of the longread articles requires more time to be read, advertisement may be easily profiled according to the text topic and be targeted for the respective reader. Future belongs to non-conservative publishers who apply innovative technologies to familiar narrative forms as the „longread”. Transition to internet and then to mobile devices is heavy for the publishers. The transition to zero user’s interface (without interface), to virtual reality, artificial intellect and machine training – all these steps will be impetuous and stormy. For publishers who ambitiously desire to survive in a time of great change it is of fundamental importance strongly

to emphasize on the changes in reader's behaviours, not only on investment in technological changes. (Long read 2017)

Still longread is apprehended as an experiment without any visible future. However, the situation in today's crossmedia and transmedia information environment indicates that attraction and detention of reader's attention is becoming more and more difficult, and this is a well-established fact. The advent of a media phenomenon like „longread” is giving us one of the decisions for the conversion of reading not just in an education process and a technique for science communicating of but also in a new type of information experience for the readers who are rather tired of being in a hurry in this dynamic 21st century.

DISCUSSION: REASONS FOR THE RISE OF THE LONGREAD

It may seem rather paradoxically but already in the end of the 20th century it has become clear that information may 'involve' the individual to pendulate between two absolutely extreme options: non-informativity and super-informativity, restriction of information freedom and going too far demanding freedom, information enslavement and information anarchy. Each individual choice of reading techniques is somewhere in-between these alternative positions that, on their own accounts, are theoretically free from any clouds and mist, doubt and confusion. Only a reader who may discover the balance between fanaticism and scepticism, cosmopolitanism and egocentrism, 'pilgrimage' and 'tourism' may manage to save him/herself from the information dissonance.

The question of our immediate interesting is put in this context as well: what are the probable motives, separately in publisher's and reader's mind, to select the exact longread formats which each of them is really selecting?

1. Brevity is in collision with the path to intellectual superiority

Reading is an exclusively intellectual process. According to George Mead, American sociologist, each intellectual activity (thorough reading is such) is characterized by a 'discontinuation of behaviour', retardness, postponement of reactions (Mead, 1997: 361). If the reading person could look at him/herself with a sidelong glance, s/he would indicate an alienation between the individual conscience and the own body. In a situation defined as 'here and now' the observer will register reader's external inertness and 'social non-attendance'.

However, in his work "The Tyranny of the Moment" (2001) Thomas Eriksen, professor in social anthropology at the University of Oslo, makes an alarming generalization: „In the information era it is practically impossible one to think definitely over any idea. The deep contentions are permanently interrupted by new fragmented pieces of information“ (Eriksen 2001: 5). Just a few years later in the dawn of Facebook and Twitter civilizationally confirmed communication cycle of 'writing-reading-citation' has been technogenicly converted in 'phrase-replica-duplica' or, using the technological slang, in the 'tweet-retweet-retweet ad infinitum' cycle.

Meanwhile, right in that time, the demands to the reader, who is getting to know, to think and to construct social reality, have been immeasurably increased: the speed of one's reactions ought not to be on the account of thought economy and based on a smattering of knowledge. When it is a matter of a complex discursive thinking, the consistent reading matter is the only one that spells out the fundamental text project (Jean-François Barbier-Bouvet). However, in the euphoria about social online media the readers have almost voluntarily surrendered in front of coercion of the diagonal reading technique. Considerable number new readers have been feeling incapable to cope with organization and management of thought, and, step by step, they could go away and apart from this process.

New forms of abridging and resuming the old classic books, big in sized and hard for reading, are providing comfort in the new technological environment; however, in parallel to them, the danger author's thinking process to be segmented while reading has been also under consideration (Tsvetkova 2007). For example, John Lock's opinion of segmentation the Bible in chapters and verses is not forgotten, yet. In his view, 'God's speech' flows like a steady and contiguous thought and the secondary 'arrangement' of the page is obliterating the unique 'drift' and harmony. The danger to „cut up“ is not just related to the idea of how adequately common people would read and perceive the respective text but it relates also to the chance a sect may get to manipulate their minds, using just one and sole excerpt from the Holy Book, to extract it out of the context, to interpret and convert it into a 'incontestable' argument about its own individual legitimacy as a sect.

Since ancient times it is publicly well-known that *Self-education reading* guarantees the mental superiority of the person and that it has to be apprehended as a slow, long, consequent and hard intellectual activity aiming to accumulate and renew the intellectual fund and

knowledge reserve of each human being as a social individual. In other words, reading is activity supporting people to overcome ignorance and is fundamental for each and every living creature. Jose Ortega y Gasset summarizes, “*God knows everything, and therefore, he does not come to know. But Man is a living insufficiency. Man needs knowledge, not ignorance, and in his lack of knowledge he is getting desperate.*”

Moreover, the availability of barriers, contradictions and discrepancies and whatever provocative elements also raises the text’s information level, and hence – of the reader as well, since they are perceived as conflicts which s/he should solve because obliged. So, barriers, the moving mechanism of intellectual excellence, should be non-standard, non-routine and time-consuming. If textual difficulties understood as barriers and their surmounting are the secret of human mental development, then short reading texts are the restraints of this development.

In such a sense, to conceive a passion for short texts reading, the so-called ‘diet reading’ confronts reader with numerous entropic risks and one of them is infantility risk. By definition, infantility means to drop behind the rest in making satisfactory and sufficient decisions under the pressure of the real rather intricate social context. In case of infantility risk one observes orientation to local, archaic equalizing values and minimization of personal capacity to make effective decisions while facing complex obstacles and sophisticated problems. Infantility, per se, may occur in various forms: reductionism or relativism; desire to copy others’ modes in a simplified form; getting some outcomes without compulsory prerequisites guaranteed; desire to generalize resolutions when detailed analysis is needed or, vice versa, to break in fragments while to act globally is the needed action. (Akhiezer 1991: 212) The passion to use short texts because of a ‘diet reading’ means to take the risk of infantilization and the probability to get mental anorexia and/or intellectual bulimia, as well. More accurately said, in this case we do not have in mind readers with special educational needs but those, disposed to laziness, who are literate individuals and, otherwise, have unlimited intellectual capacities. And it is rather unpleasantly to think how daily life converts into forcefully harmed creatures persons who otherwise are not harmed by faith but blessed by birth.

2. To be in a hurry while reading means to be in a collision with understanding and rationalization

It seems, the mainstreamers (mainstream trainers) in speed reading and the technology companies with their software, used in the mass service activities, are rather speculative while dealing in their propaganda affairs with the skepticism of Anatole France's wry remark "*Life is too short and Proust is too long.*"

The most troublesome issue in the speedy reading programs concerns observation that a query for the participants about meaningful and worthy information, contented in the respective texts, does never occur in their monitoring studies. Such tests, evaluating the training effect of speedy reading, are checking-up word identification process but not its understanding as well. One of the most renowned experts in the specific field of how the eyes are involved in the reading, Keith Rayner, a psychologist, after decades of systematic researches of reading speed, finally has come to the convincing conclusion that the speedy readers are inefficient. During the exam they were demonstrating relatively good reactions to the general questions concerning the text; they caught their answers while running 'like horses' through the various fragments, and the information gaps they were filling out on grounds of previously obtained knowledge in respect to the discussed issues. However, when asked about the details, they failed. The leading concept for Keith Rayner and her colleagues today is that at the level of mechanics (identification of words and phrases) one may get just a speedy reading but cannot be successful in understanding. The speed of reading, *de facto*, is not a constant variable for the different people. Everyone uses various paces which always depend on the way of ranking difficulty and on the final goal of the reading task. (Rayner 2016)

The speed, with which we are reading whatever kind of text, should serve our ability to *remember* it more solidly and for a longer time. It is logically, a priority in fast reading advertisements should be given to the assumption that if the speed is raised, the text is memorized in 70 per cent better. However, the recent findings of neurolinguists and cognitive psychologists demonstrate something else – better (more durable) memorizing as a reading effect can be obtained if the process, itself, is slowed and disciplined via a difficult for spelling out print type. More complex and difficult, rich and flagrant the text type is (parameters of the serif type), more time it takes to identify, to pick out the single word, and it leads to stronger skills to remember the message; such is the final conclusion of Conner Diemand-Yauman and Daniel Oppenheimer's study (Diemand-Yauman et al. 2010). I would add that this research is

actively cited in today studies and scholars' reviews of reader literacy because, experimentally, it gives evidence for the fact that non-serif print types, soundly promoted by Microsoft, although they have some privileges in the process of easy decoding, cannot help in the other process – of memorizing and retaining the information obtained, its meaning. However, from the viewpoint of psychology of communication design, if the reader possesses more knowledge about the richness of the very glyph configurations, s/he would extract more content while identifying and decoding them (in harmony with the saying “*More you know, more you see*”). Previous and consequent investigations are still more hardening another concept – the thesis that the increased non-readability of the text presses the reader to scrutinize the words which means a richer and deeper memory and better meta-understanding.

In speed reading procedure one precariously tries to escape the phase, accountable for making sense of the contents. This effect is mostly visible while reading fiction. Mind ‘talking’ is a process that makes the reader to feel empathy of the story told, to mark the characters and to shape the objects in own individual manner. In fast reading these so-called mini-pauses and delays absent which, in fact, is a limitation of imagination. Advocates of the slow literary reading clarify that just in this way the effect of repeated reading may be reinforced and only due to the slow pace reader may get more intellectual feast. In order s/he to be fascinated by the creative mastership of the author/writer and to throw off the constrains of his/her imagination, it is necessary to make pauses and to miss none of the various text components. The maximum level which may be reached in speedy reading may be climbed up if a chance to a speedy data processing in a huge textual amount has been given in advance. (Carbonell 2012)

All above mentioned considerations make impossible the definition of real benefits from high-speed reading achievements and may be used as sufficient merits to provoke mistrust to similar services, even more self-active recently, concerning the process of information (media and digital) literacy reinforcement. Maybe, speedy reading achieves the effect of fast perception and memorization but the complex cognitive functions, such as *understanding, rationalization*, are possible only in case of maintenance the step in a tempo rate as *largo* → *lento* → *adagio* (the most slow tempos in music).

3. Speed means a collision with nature of reading

In the 21st century rapidity becomes a basic index of effectiveness, and speed – the most fashionable fetish. It is expected, in all daily activities connected with service and communication, rapidity and timeliness to be fundamental criteria. Today's mobile Homo Informaticus prefers to have all happenings around him/her maximum proportionately to the pace of one's own life. Again and again this pace becomes more and more speedy, i.e. in accordance with the fast music tempo *allegro* → *presto* → *prestissimo*.

It is well-known fact, the permeable filtering human body capacities are rather restricted. Human mind perceives almost all outer signals but processes only the stronger ones. In a case of an enhanced intensity of the information flow, however, the recipient decreases his/her perceptive sensitivity toward the feeble signals and the brain receives limited variety of information from narrowly taken-in messages. So, conditions for a narrow-grounded knowledge occur; such a knowledge is backing solely to a factual information, usually quite clashing and contradictory. When events and changes in the surroundings occur faster than usually, man is able to react only selectively to single, isolated, individual phenomena while in case of a normal dynamics selective reaction, per se, keeps him/her away from mistakes and failures.

What are the experimentally proved data (Eljakov 2005: 114-121)?

⇒ Today data quantity, in-flowing into human mind, is minimum of 100 000 bps and in reality it is possible to perceive and use between 25 and 100 bps (Semenjuk 1988: 132).

⇒ The biggest data quantity that could be apprehended by the reader is calculated in units per second: reading silently – 45 units per second, reading aloud – 30 units per second, proof-reading – 18 units per second.

⇒ The capacity of human brain allows information introduced to be assimilated (perceiving and processing) in a maximal speed of 25 bps.; having in mind this limited capacity and the fact that per day we are reading around 50 text pages, it means that during our whole life we may read not more than 3000 books.

⇒ The speed of transmitting the nerve signal in human body is maximum 30 000 symbols per second while the computer signals are moved and processed millions of time faster. In the field of data transmission via internet only in 2016 several world records were registered: first, researchers from London University, the UK, achieved a speed of 1,125 Tbps.; later, at the International Economic Forum in Saint Petersburg, Russia, there was a demonstration of speedy

mobile internet of 1,24 Gb/s. In other words, all episodes of the *Game of Thrones* Series in HD may be downloaded ‘all in the same breath’, i.e. for less than one second (Maher 2016; MegaFon 2016).

⇒ Big Data phenomenon - this unbelievable speed of today’s changes, is happening in parallel with the enormous data growth – over 90 per cent of the whole produced digital contents is non-structural information (Schubmehl 2014).

We may try to formulate also the effects on the reader’s intellectual capacity in respect to the non-ergonomic speed of communications and information. Findings about information overload and information stress of Profs. Thomas Eriksen, Anatolij Eljakov and Daniel Levitin have been used (Eriksen 2001: 59-60; Eljakov 2005: 120; Levitin 2017):

1. Human Being automatically „erases“ from the operation memory old data from the current information flow in order to free space for the newer, richer and multiple frequentative messages.

2. Human Being retains rather small portion of the perceived current information because the messages, in general, are submitted chaotically, fragmentally, out of any logic order and structure.

3. Human Being does not catch in the whole volume of information (missing a part of the information) because of time-lack to watch it (listen).

4. Human Being multiplies his/her mistakes, loses exactness and accuracy in upshots for lack of time to check-up and talk over own actions.

5. Human Being perceives, processes and remolds the whole information exactly and in compliance with the task but after the deadline.

6. Human Being perceives information distorted in form as it has been received non-structurally, and this turns into a source for creating incorrect picture of the facts, on the one hand, and for false decisions, on the other.

7. Human Being refuses to apprehend information because s/he does not manage to follow out and to study it.

8. Human Being falls down in short temper, even in panic, when understands s/he has not taken in or remembered the full information of the topic interested in.

9. Human Being loses self-confidence because of accelerating rates of his/her activity, working against time and diminishing lines between leisure and work hours, when hears more frequently rebukes like “Come on, there’s no time!”; as a result s/he falls back on pharmacological methods (antidepressants) while solving the problems. Acceleration and uncertainty are directly proportional, as Paul Virilio asserts in his „La machine de vision“ (Virilio 1988).

10. Human Being willingly becomes hostage of simplification of intellectual operations, an occurrence envisaged as a promotion of liberation from suffering, escape from mental tortures in the era of very high speeds. Such is the propaganda style of Prof. Michael Dertouzos from the MIT, one of the WEB ideology founding fathers. In 1997 he promised simplification of the mental work via ‘electronic bulldozers’ with perfect humanist arguments: „more contacts than we may remember, more complexity than we may manage, higher speed than we may master – if we allow all this stuff to overload us, we shall suffer from stress and shall be ineffective.” (Dertouzos 2001: 400). However, side by side with this phenomenon, simplifications implant in consumer’s mind the false feeling for power over nature of belongings, household goods, chattels, etc., and even over world’s structure and fabrics.

11. Human Being easily amputates his/her own sense of responsibility as the speed constructs the ‘conveyer effect’ and the ‘relay race effect “ – you give the next athlete on the road a signal and breathe a sigh of relief turning out yourself from any commitment and obligation.

12. Human Being deforms one’s written habits as the speed influences on syntaxes and style. Typical example is ‘texting’ phenomenon, a written SMS slang, criticized by Howard Rheingold in his „Smart Mobs“ long since 2002 (Rheingold 2002).

13. Human Being destroys his/her capacities to be thinkable, studious and creative because of a very acute time deficit.

Especially relevant to the now described situation is the episod from the famous *Winnie-the Pooh* when the teddy bear has been dragged downstairs by Christopher Robin, and with hit head it is thinking: ‘Oh! Just if I have a time to stop and to think!’. (Let’s remember the popular English musical *Stop the World I Want to Get Off*). Acceleration is not the most comfortable bus-stop on the development road of humanity. From the physics we have learnt that overspeed

changes the shape. However, the modern man has no other choice: if s/he does not enter this competition, simply s/he will remain behind on the 'station platform'. (Tsvetkova 2016b)

4. Reader's attention is the new hard currency

Online media publishers are facing an actual trouble and it implicitly re-enforces their anxiety as for the slipping reader; this problem is named 'information economy' is substituted by 'attention economy', and it gains more grounds (Bard 2002). In the modern world, totally mediated and mutually-non-transparently networked, with typography that looks like an ancient Greek labyrinth, with information overproduction and 'netocratic' power, attention occurs to be the only unique hard currency (Peicheva 2016). And attention, on its behalf, becomes even more deficient than money as a resource (money is a product of attention, not vice versa). Therefore, the exchange in the 'media-reader' system has already been transformed into an interchange of 'attention vs. attention'. It is exactly attractivity that is converted into a serious capital and becomes the most valuable assets of longread technology. With its support the qualitative journalism is getting back to the spotlight at the central stage.

CONCLUSIONS

The researchers, anxious about the dropdowns of the attentive reading levels, have their serious arguments] they are sorry for the transition, we are passing through, to online social networks, blogs, twits and any other partialized communications. It is true, if there is a desire to learn and even more, in case of a research process, it is necessary to concentrate on search for the meanings of the single words, key phrases and verbatim citations. However, we cannot agree that understanding the meaning of any individual word will bring us the very same full-length picture about the respective topic as if we are reading the entire book. Therefore, the healthy mind of the intelligent reader re-discovers the long reading forms even in the online environment. The long, concentrated and patient reading from the display is not in a regress.

Registered recurring cycle in 'lengthy twist' in the reading proposals has shown that any transfer toward shorter books is likely to be a step toward long books. All we can hope for is that the 'natural length' of each book will be respected.

It was registered as well that longread phenomenon is directly depending on the changes in the media consumerism and on actual psycho-cognitive re-tuning of the readers, a process including:

- time availability;
- patience;
- concentration;
- self-control;
- personal interest;
- curiosity;
- sustainable information hygiene;
- awared need for media diet;
- expressed necessity authentically and affluently (high calories) to get knowledge and not just ‘excursionist informativity’ or ‘touristic orientation’.

Longread is a reading with a style. But longread is a niche, non-mastered yet by the publishers and advertisers. Still is apprehended as an experiment. However, the situation in today’s crossmedia and transmedia information environment indicates that attraction and detention of reader’s attention is becoming more and more difficult. The media phenomenon „longread” is giving us one of the decisions for the conversion of reading not just in an education process and a technique for science popularisation, of but also in a new type of information experience for the frustrated readers.

The challenge in front of the research community is to make a qualified study, analyzing the young readers’ attitudes to longreads and long-time e-reading, and to initiate in-depth studies among the creators of media contents (editorial councils) for their general understanding of the long-text form. Another direction of future research is to look from the opposite side – what kind of social, political, psychical, emotional trends are revealed by each and every specific ‘lengthy twist’ of the reading formats. If the production growth of longread publishing forms has to be observed, most probably such a growth may be the answer will be in information alterations of the reading society demands that are non-convertible and predicting various surprises. This is a fundamental reason to keep an eye on acts and manifestations and perspectives of the longread phenomenon in the Bulgarian publishing environment.

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APPENDIX

LONG-READ	Year	SHORT-READ
	1968	"Easy-to-read", Sweden
	1970–1982	Infographics
	1980	"Drabble", 100 words
"Harry Potter" Book Series 	1997–2007	
	2000	"Key to the Classics", Cliffs Notes
	2005	"The 100-Minute Bible"
	2006	Twitter, 140-character tweet
Longreads blog 		
Instant publishing	2010–2011	

<p>TED Books</p>		
<p>Kindle Singles, Amazon</p> <p>In short, a great read</p>		
<p>Longread "Snow Fall"</p>	2012	
<p>Facebook "Instant Articles"</p>	2016	
<p>Editions at Play</p>		
<p>Twitter</p>	2016, September	
<p>Facebook "Instant Articles"</p>	2017	
<p>Twitter, 280-character tweet</p>	2017, November	